

Study of Blood Coagulation Disorders and their Assessment by Thromboelastography in Patients with Sepsis in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Sepsis is a life threatening and body's extreme response to an infection and is a medical emergency which may cause coagulation disorders like hypo coagulation and hyper coagulation state, using parameters like PT, aPTT, Fibrinogen, D-dimer and Thromboelastography which helps in early detection of these disorders so mortality and morbidity can be prevented. This study tries to find their relationship in identifying these blood coagulation state.

Material and Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional hospital-based study was done in Department of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur on sepsis patients admitted in ICU or HDU. Blood coagulation parameters were noted, and TEG was done and relationship between them was sought.

Results: In sepsis patients PT, aPTT, D dimer and serum lactate levels were disarranged and were significantly positively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 and significantly negatively correlated with Alpha and MA of TEG. Also, fibrinogen level, WBC and serum albumin was significantly negatively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 and significantly positively correlated with Alpha and MA of TEG.

Conclusion: TEG parameters correlate well with blood coagulation defects in sepsis patients. Blood coagulation parameters and TEG can effectively detect the coagulation defects in sepsis patients to reduce mortality and morbidity.

Keywords: Thromboelastography, coagulation defect, sepsis, TEG, PT, Aptt.

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Introduction

Sepsis is life-threatening organ dysfunction caused by a dysregulated host response to infection.[1] In 2017 there were 48.9 million cases of sepsis and 11 million deaths due to sepsis worldwide (20% of all global death). Health care-associated infections are one of the majority cause of infection and affect millions of patients worldwide every year.[2,3]

Sepsis is defined as the systemic immune response syndrome (SIRS). The diagnosis of sepsis was based on the presence of a suspected infection and clinical or microbiological evidence of infection in the presence of at least two of the four systemic inflammatory response criteria (SIRS). In addition to sepsis, the term severe sepsis is defined as sepsis associated with organ dysfunction, hypoperfusion and hypotension, and the term septic shock as a condition of sepsis with arterial hypotension insen-

sitive to fluid replacement.[4] Sepsis may lead to disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC). Acute DIC is decompensated DIC in which there is rapid systemic activation of coagulation leading to consumption of platelets and coagulation factors which is more than production.

Later on leading to increased number of thrombi, increased fibrinolysis, increased fibrin degradation products and it prevent new clot formation and platelet aggregation. All these ultimately leads to severe clinical bleeding/ hemorrhage and thrombotic end organ damage[5]. Thromboelastography (TEG) measures the global viscoelastic properties of whole blood clot formation. TEG measures the parameters in form of R time, K time, MA (maximum amplitude) and alpha angle. In case of hypo-coagulability R and K time is prolonged and /or

MA and alpha angle is prolonged. In case of hyper-coagulable state there is shortened reaction times (R and/ or K) and enhanced clot formation as expressed by increased alpha and/or high maximal amplitude (MA).[6] So this study tries to compare the assessment of coagulation disorder in sepsis patients by blood coagulation parameters versus the same assessment by thromboelastography (TEG).

Material and Methods

A descriptive cross sectional hospital based study was done in Department of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur on patients admitted in ICU diagnosed as sepsis according to sepsis 3 criteria as per Surviving Sepsis campaign.[7] Due ethical clearance was taken from institutional ethical committee. Systematic Random Selection of every 3rd patient admitted in ICU and diagnosed as Sepsis within the study period was done and consent was taken. Blood coagu-

lation parameters like platelet count, PT, aPTT, D dimer and fibrinogen level; blood infection parameters like WBC count, serum albumin and serum lactate level and TEG parameters were monitored and compared.

Results

In this study there were total 168 sepsis patients. The study subjects were of age 18 to 65 yrs with most of the study subject i.e 42 (25%) belonged to age group 31 to 40 yrs followed by 11 (6.5%), 34(20.2%), 34 (20.2%), 35 (20.8%) and 12 (7.1%) respectively. The mean was 40.36 yrs and the SD 13.38. In this study 98(58.3%) study subjects were male and 70 (41.7%) were female with male to female ratio was 1.4:1. In this study 61(36.3%) did not have any co-morbidity followed by 40 (23.8%), 49 (29.2%), 11 (6.5%), 4 (2.4%) and 3 (1.8%) were suffering from diabetes, hypertension, hypothyroidism, asthma and tuberculosis respectively.

Table 1: Distribution of study subject according to Blood Coagulation lab parameters

TEG	R (min)	K (min)	Alpha ⁰	MA (mm)	CL30 (%)
Mean (SD)	17.80 (13.37)	4.04 (2.60)	56.71 (23.35)	52.17 (19.59)	8.99 (5.06)
Blood coagulation parameter	Platelet (Per mcL)	PT (Seconds)	aPTT (Seconds)	Fibrinogen (mg/dl)	DDimer IU/ml
Mean (SD)	47331 (19581)	21.86 (11.39)	54.15 (26.26)	250.10 (197.97)	1.31 (1.58)
Blood Infection Parameters	WBC Units/mcL		Albumin (gm/dl)	Lactate (m mol/L)	
Mean(SD)	16532 (12369)		2.62(0.44)	4.73 (1.13)	

(N=168)

On doing TEG the mean values came as R value 17.80 min (SD 13.37), K value 4.04 min(SD 2.60, Alpha angle 56.71⁰ (SD 23.35), MA value 52.17 mm (SD 19.59) and CL 30 value is 8.99% (SD 5.06). The mean blood coagulation laboratory parameters as platelets count, PT, aPTT, fibrinogen level and D Dimer level was 47331/mcL (SD 19581), 21.86 seconds (SD11.39), 54.15 Seconds

(SD 26.26), 250.10 mg/dl (SD 197.97) and 1.31 IU/ml (SD 1.58) respectively. The mean WBC count of the sepsis patient was 16532 / mcL (SD 12369), mean albumin was 2.62 gm/dl (SD 0.44) and mean lactate was 4.73 m mol/L (SD 1.13). Out of total 168 sepsis patient 115 (68.5%) were in hypo-coagulation state and rest 53 (31.5%) were in hyper-coagulation state.

Table 2: Correlation between TEG and blood coagulation parameters

Parameters	R	K	Alpha	MA	CL30	
TEG VS Blood Coagulation Parameters						
Platelet Count	R	0.638	0.802	-0.887	-0.867	0.839
	P	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
PT	R	0.995	0.963	-0.919	-0.935	0.950
	P	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
aPTT	R	0.975	0.994	-0.981	-0.987	0.992
	P	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Fibrinogen Level	R	-0.883	-0.965	0.995	0.990	-0.982
	P	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
D Dimer Level	R	0.699	0.640	-0.563	-0.585	0.605
	P	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
TEG Vs Blood Infection Parameters						
WBC	R	-0.290	-0.352	0.349	0.341	-0.321

	P	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Serum Albumin	R	-0.650	-0.561	0.442	0.460	-0.494
	P	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Serum Lactate	R	0.678	0.546	-0.413	-0.441	0.480
	P	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

As shown in the table platelet count is significantly positively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 value with r value 0.638, 0.802 and 0.839 respectively and p value 0.000. But the platelet count is significantly negatively correlated with Alpha angle and MA value with r value -0.887 and -0.867 respectively and p value 0.000. Similarly,

PT is significantly positively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 value with r value 0.995, 0.963 and 0.950 respectively and p value 0.000. But the PT is significantly negatively correlated with Alpha angle and MA value with r value -0.919 and -0.935 respectively and p value 0.000.

Figure 1: Scatter Plot showing relationship between R/K value of TEG and PT/aPTT

The aPTT is significantly positively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 value with r value 0.975, 0.994 and 0.992 respectively and p value 0.000. But the aPTT is significantly negatively correlated with Alpha angle and MA value with r value -0.981 and -0.987 respectively and p value 0.000. D Dimer is significantly positively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 value with r value 0.699, 0.640 and 0.605 respectively and p value 0.000. But the D Dimer is significantly negatively

correlated with Alpha angle and MA value with r value -0.563 and -0.585 respectively and p value 0.000. But Fibrinogen level is significantly negatively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 value with r value- 0.883, -0.965 and- 0.982 respectively and p value 0.000. But the fibrinogen is significantly positively correlated with Alpha angle and MA value with r value 0.995 and 0.990 respectively and p value 0.000.

Figure 2: Scatter Plot showing relationship between Alpha/MA value of TEG and PT/aPTT

As shown in the table WBC count is significantly negatively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 value with r value - 0.290, -0.352 and -0.321 respectively and p value 0.000. But the WBC count is significantly positively correlated with Alpha angle and MA value with r value 0.349 and 0.341 respectively and p value 0.000. Serum Albumin is significantly negatively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 value with r value -0.650, -0.561 and -0.494 respectively and p value 0.000. But the

Serum albumin is significantly positively correlated with Alpha angle and MA value with r value 0.442 and 0.460 respectively and p value 0.000. Serum Lactate is significantly positively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 value with r value 0.678, 0.546 and 0.480 respectively and p value 0.000. But the serum lactate is significantly negatively correlated with Alpha angle and MA value with r value -0.413 and -0.441 respectively and p value 0.000.

Table 3: Distribution of study subject according coagulation state

Coagulation state	Frequency	Percent
Hypo-coagulation state	115	68.5
Hyper-coagulation state	53	31.5
Total	168	100.0

As shown in the table out of total 168 sepsis patient 115 (68.5%) were in hypo-coagulation state and rest 53 (31.5%) were in hyper-coagulation state. Among the age group <20 yrs 10 (90.9%) and 1 (9.1%) study subject; among 21-30 yrs age group 23 (67.6%) and 11 (32.4%) study subject; among age group 31-40 yrs age group 30 (71.4%) and 12 (28.6%) study subject; among 41-50 age group 23 (67.6%) and 11 (32.4%) study subject; among 51-60 yrs age group 21 (60.0%) and 14 (40.0%) and

finally among more than 60 yrs age group 8 (66.7%) and 4 (33.3%) study subject were in hypo-coagulation and hypercoagulation state respectively. This difference was not statistically significant. ($p>0.05$) In this study among males 69 (70.4%) and 29 (29.6%); and among females 46 (65.7%) and 24 (34.3%) were in hypo coagulation and hyper coagulation state respectively. This difference was not statistically significant. ($p>0.05$).

Figure 3: Distribution of study subject according coagulation state

Discussion

Organ dysfunction caused by a deregulated host response to infection is called Sepsis[1] Sepsis patients often need invasive procedures, and coagulopathy is often a complication of the condition. In sepsis patients, an imbalance between the production of clots (coagulation) and their disintegration (fibrinolysis) is a major reaction coming from host defense mechanisms that can result in organ failure.[8]

The viscoelastic hemostatic assay known as thromboelastography (TEG) examines the global viscoelastic characteristics of whole blood clot formation under modest shear stress. It is not necessarily correlated with blood tests such as the INR, APTT, and platelet count, which are sometimes less accu-

rate predictors of bleeding and thrombosis.[6,9] This study tries to compare the assessment of coagulation disorder in sepsis patients by blood coagulation parameters versus the same assessment by thromboelastography (TEG). There were total 168 sepsis patients of age 18 to 65 yrs with most of the study subject i.e 42 (25%) belonged to age group 31 to 40 yrs. The mean was 40.36 yrs and the SD 13.38. In this study 98(58.3%) study subjects were male and 70 (41.7%) were female with male to female ratio was 1.4:1. Kim et al[10] in 2020 studied the role of thromboelastography in prediction of shock. Mean age of the study subject was 65.6 ± 12.7 years and 58.6% were male. Zhou et al.[11] in 2019 in a similar study on 81 sepsis patients found the average age to be 59.14 ± 13.42 years and there were 52 males (64.2%) and 29 females (35.8%). In

a prospective, observational study done on ICU patients, Muzaffar et al.[12] in 2017 enrolled 55 ICU patients to evaluate the coagulopathy by thrombo-elastography (TEG).

The mean age was mean age was 45.6 (± 17) years and 62% were males. In this study 61(36.3%) did not have any co-morbidity followed by 40 (23.8%), 49 (29.2%), 11 (6.5%), 4 (2.4%) and 3 (1.8%) were suffering from diabetes, hypertension, hypothyroidism, asthma and tuberculosis respectively. In a study by Tian et al.[13] in 2022 who studied dynamic APACHE score in ICU patients found comorbidities that were prevalent were hypertension (26.5%), diabetes (14.2%), liver disease (8.4%), CKD (10%), heart failure (20.5%), stroke (8.3%) and anemia (7.2%) Co morbidities present in study by Kim et al.[10] in 2020 were hypertension(35.3%), diabetes (25.5%), chronic pulmonary disease (10%), hematologic disease (6.2%), malignancy (47.8%), chronic renal disease (6.6%), and chronic liver disease (15.9%). So overall these sepsis patients were suffering from various co morbidities which may be a factor for the poor prognosis or worsening of the condition. Muzaffar et al.[12] in 2017 found medical illness in 76% and comorbidities (such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, and chronic kidney disease) in 60% of sepsis patient.

The mean blood coagulation laboratory parameters as platelets count, PT, aPTT, fibrinogen level and D Dimer level was 47331/mcL (SD 19581), 21.86 seconds (SD11.39), 54.15 Seconds (SD 26.26), 250.10 mg/dl (SD 197.97) and 1.31 IU/ml (SD 1.58) respectively. The mean WBC count of the sepsis patient was 16532 / mcL (SD 12369), mean albumin was 2.62 gm/dl (SD 0.44) and mean lactate was 4.73 m mol/L (SD 1.13). Out of total 168 sepsis patient 115 (68.5%) were in hypo-coagulation state and rest 53 (31.5%) were in hyper-coagulation state. In the study by Kim et al.[10] in 2020 the lab parameters include WBC count 11.8+10.7, Hb 10.7+ 2.4, BUN 31.1+ 20.3, creatinine 2 + 2.3, albumin 2.7 +1.6, lactate 4.1 + 3.1, platelet count 161.9 \pm 114.1, PT 1.47 \pm 0.91, aPTT 34.5 \pm 15.9, D dimer 4.6 (2.2–10.6). Zhou et al.[11] in 2019 in a similar study found the lab parameters as APTT, 27.6–34.3 sec; TT, 10.3–16.6 sec; PT, 9.9–12.8 sec; PTA, 70–130%; FIB, 2.0–4.6 g/l; DD, <1.5 mg/l, FDP, 0–5 μ g/ml. Blood routine: PLT, 100–300 \times 10⁹/l. So as different patients were in different stage of sepsis severity so blood coagulation and sepsis parameter are different in different studies.

In our study on doing TEG the mean values came as R value 17.80 min (SD 13.37), K value 4.04 min(SD 2.60, Alpha angle 56.710 (SD 23.35), MA value 52.17 mm (SD 19.59) and CL 30 value is 8.99% (SD 5.06). Kim et al.[10] in 2020 found mean (SD)TEG value be 6.9(6.7), 2.6(3.9),

61.6(15.8), 61.3(14.5), 1.2(6.2) respectively. Muzaffar et al.[12] in 2017 in a similar study found, mean(SD) values of R, K, α , MA, CI, and LY30 were 6.45 \pm 2.59 (min), 1.67 \pm 0.96 (min), 66.37 \pm 10.44 (0), 67.08 \pm 10.33 (mm), 0.63 \pm 3.46, and 2.23 \pm 4.08 (%), respectively. Similarly, 6.9(SD 6.7), 2.6(SD 3.9), 61.6(SD 15.8), 61.3(Sd 14.5), 1.2(6.2) respectively. Zhou et al.[11] in 2019 found TEG values as R value, 5–10 min; MA value, 50–70 mm; α angle, 53–72 deg; K time, 1–3 min; CI, –3 to 3; LY30, –3–4.0%. Kilic et al.[14] in 2014 found significant differences in Sepsis and Control between the TEG values (R, K, α angle, and MA) at day 1 and day 3.

In our study platelet count was significantly positively correlated with R value, K value and platelet count was significantly negatively correlated with Alpha angle and MA value. ($p < 0.001$). PT was significantly positively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 value and PT was significantly negatively correlated with Alpha angle and MA value. ($p < 0.001$). aPTT was significantly positively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 value and aPTT was significantly negatively correlated with Alpha angle and MA, ($p < 0.001$). D Dimer was significantly positively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 value but D Dimer was significantly negatively correlated with Alpha angle and MA value. ($p < 0.001$). This gives a picture that as blood coagulation parameters like PT, aPTT and D Dimer increase it causes increase in R, K and CL30 and decrease of alpha and MA which gives picture of hypo-coagulation state.

In our study WBC count was significantly negatively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 value and it was significantly positively correlated with Alpha angle and MA value($p < 0.001$).

Serum Albumin was significantly negatively correlated with R value, K value and CL30, but the Serum albumin was significantly positively correlated with Alpha angle and MA value. Serum Lactate was significantly positively correlated with R value, K value and CL30 value, but the serum lactate was significantly negatively correlated with Alpha angle and MA value. Other studies had the similar findings. Kim et al.[10] in 2020 also found that DIC group had significantly lower levels of hemoglobin and albumin and higher initial level of lactate than the non-DIC group. Zhou et al.[11] in 2019 found that at the time of ICU entry, compared with sepsis group, K time in septic shock group was significantly longer than that of sepsis group and the angle α , MA value and CI decreased significantly while LY30 increased significantly. After 6 h, ICU entry, compared with sepsis group, R value and K time of the septic shock group were significantly prolonged, while the MA value, CI, and α angle were significantly decreased and LY30 was significantly increased. So as sepsis severity in-

creases the TEG parameters changes in such a way to indicate hypocoagulable state. Muzaffar et al.[12] in 2017 found that patients with septic shock had lower alpha, MA, and CI values) while those without shock had higher alpha, MA, and CI values which indicates a hypocoagulable state. Overall, 56% patients were normocoagulable, 27% hypercoagulable, and 17% hypocoagulable. In our study 115(68.45%) were in hypocoagulable state and 53(31.55%) were in hypercoagulable state. In patients with normal INR, 15% patients were hypocoagulable and 32% were hypercoagulable and in those with deranged INR (INR \geq 1.6), 60% were normocoagulable and 20% were hypercoagulable. Similarly, 81% patients with thrombocytopenia were normocoagulable and in patients with normal fibrinogen levels, 9% were hypocoagulable and 27% were hypercoagulable. So, the blood coagulation parameters as INR, platelet count, fibrinogen levels are not reliable indicator of coagulation status. But we found a significant relationship between TEG and blood coagulation parameters. Kilic et al.[14] in 2014 when compared control and sepsis group with regard to basic SIRS criteria, significant differences were found in all criteria ($P < 0.05$). At day 1 significant differences between the 2 groups were found in hemoglobin, hematocrit, WBC, PLT, PT, aPTT, INR, and PCT values At day 3 hemoglobin, hematocrit, and aPTT values were not significantly different ($P > 0.05$). In our study blood coagulation parameters are significantly correlated to TEG parameters. The R value in Group S was lower than that of Group C at day 1 and day 2 ($P < 0.05$), the K value was lower in Group S at day 1 ($P < 0.05$), and the alpha value was higher in Group S at day 1 ($P < 0.05$) which indicates the condition to be a hypercoagulable state.

In our study age and gender is not significantly related to blood coagulation status. ($p > 0.05$). Zhou et al.[11] in 2019 also did not found significant differences in the patient's sex, age and other basic data among sepsis group, APACHE II score group, DIC group, TEG index and SOFA score correlation group and prognosis group.

Conclusion

Sepsis is a critical condition characterized by severe organ dysfunction due to the body's dysregulated response to infection, representing an urgent medical emergency. Sepsis involves coagulation disorders and abnormalities of platelet count, PT, aPTT, fibrinogen, and D-dimer. In our study TEG correlated well with blood coagulation and blood infection parameters.

So doing TEG along with measuring platelet count, PT, aPTT, fibrinogen, and D-dimer can help in detecting coagulation abnormalities early and precisely. It will help in deciding the course of treat-

ment i.e whether to give anticoagulant (In case of hyper-coagulation state of DIC) or to withhold it (In case of hypocoagulation state of DIC) and when to escalate the antibiotic therapy and resuscitation measures.

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